

Lutheran Theology Seminary

Master of Divinity

OT2021 Atonement and Forgiveness in the Bible
and Jewish Traditions

Term Paper

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Chosen Text:

2. Jesper Svartvik, *Reconciliation and Transformation: Reconsidering Christian Theologies of the Cross*. (2021)

Chapter 4 - Why Did the First Christians Stop Making Sacrifices? P.30-39

Chapter 7 - Rendering the Rending of the Veil P.72-95

Review/summary of the content.

This book comprehensively and systematically introduces readers to Christian Theologies of the Cross. Through examining the teachings and beliefs of various theologians throughout history, the author Jesper Svartvik tries to explore the true meaning of sacrifice, the relationship between Jews and Christians, and interpretations of the rending of the veil. In my opinion, the purpose of this book, as the title suggests, is to serve as a tool for reconciliation, especially between Jews and Christians, and to foster the transformation of the lives of Jesus' followers.

In Chapter 4, Jesper first examines the Pauline Epistles to eliminate the possibility that the early Christians stopped making sacrifices due to a rejection of temple services or the Jewish tradition. Instead, he shows that Paul only criticized the practice of making sacrifices to idols. Jesper also raises the question of the connection between the fallacy of the temple and the resurrection of Jesus Christ.

After the year 70 CE, both Jews and Christians found ways to survive the catastrophic destruction of the temple. Jesper highlights the differences in the approaches taken by the two groups of believers. The former is described as **sublimating** the sacrifices through means such as prayer and studying texts related to sacrifices, while the latter believed that all sacrifices had been **substituted** by the death of Jesus Christ.

Jesper also presents different scholarly interpretations of the Old Testament texts on sacrifice. Some scholars view the texts as allegorical, arguing that they should not be treated as describing real temple services. Others suggest that the Old Testament texts on sacrifice are true, but only valid for a certain time period, and no longer serve their function after the death of Jesus Christ.

Jesper acknowledges that the Christian portrayal of temple worship is somewhat biased and that the temple is depicted in a pejorative manner. The apologetic tradition also believes that after the cessation of sacrifices, the Jews could no longer obtain atonement. However, Jesper considers this to be an unjust verdict against the Jewish temple tradition. To support this, Jesper cites Rabbinic literature and portrays Jesus as a devout Jew who followed Jewish festival traditions, to demonstrate that placing Jesus, the first-generation believers, and the early Christian movement within the context of the Jewish culture of the time would lead to a more comprehensive understanding. The author attempts to guide the reader to view the Jewish cultural foundation that gave rise to Christian believers from a more objective perspective, beyond the conventional dividing lines of faith.

In Chapter 7, with the topic of "Rendering the Rending of the Veil", which is closely related to the culture of sacrifice, the author Jesper Svartvik presents three historical interpretations of the tearing of the temple veil to the readers: A Sign of God's Wrath, A Reason for Joyfulness, and An Expression of Divine Sorrow.

Regarding the interpretation of the tearing of the temple veil as a Sign of God's Wrath, Jesper examines the views of Melito, the Bishop of Sardis from the 2nd century. Melito's Easter homily "Peri Pascha" directly accuses the Jews of being responsible for the execution of Jesus (God). Some scholars believe Melito's sermon was meant to exculpate Pontius Pilate by placing the full blame on the Jews. However, Jesper questions the narrow and biased nature of Melito's preaching by examining the possible apocryphal sources of his sermon, the influence of the relationship between Jews and Christians in Sardis, and whether he was targeting the actual, real-life Jews. Jesper further cites the biblical passage about sinners casting stones to strengthen his perspective and emphasizes the dangers of this interpretation.

On the interpretation of the rent of the veil as a Reason for Joyfulness, the temple is described as symbolic of human disbelief and lack of faith. People see the temple as an obstacle to the relations between God and His people, and the torn veil no longer serves to separate people from God. Jesper argues that this is an "extremely inappropriate interpretation." He describes the temple as a place of sacred

encounter, the sanctuary like the horizon, the meeting point between heaven and earth. If one uses human joy to interpret the tearing of the veil, it would be problematic, as it would make people insensitive to pain and sorrow, and the over-emphasis on revelation theology may lead to indifference towards suffering and death.

The third interpretation, that the torn veil is an Expression of Divine Sorrow, seems to be the one that the author Jesper most agrees with. He discusses the Jewish tradition and the biblical accounts of people expressing grief by tearing their clothes when facing the death of others. He believes that when the only begotten Son died, the tearing of the veil was most likely an expression of God's sorrow. Further, he draws on the virtue of *imitatio dei*, arguing that when people consider it in this direction, their mourning for the dead will evolve into love and care for others, combining faith and ethics. This also explains that the tearing of the veil is not the first or second interpretation, and the veil is not a barrier between people and God, but rather an expression of the presence of the benevolent God.

In the final part of the chapter, the author Jesper leads the readers to re-examine the scene of Jesus' passion and its theological outcome, explaining that we should not only look at it from a historical causal perspective, as this cannot fully explain the theological significance. Through the Gospel of Mark and Paul's commission to preach reconciliation, he shows how Jesus' suffering led to a beneficial outcome.

Reflections

The two chapters of this book are both worth reading, as they provoke thought on the issues of atonement and forgiveness and also reveal the author's effort in addressing an important topic - the divisions between Judaism and Christianity. The author attempts to trace the origins and possible causes of the divisions between the two, hoping to shed light on the reasons that have led to conflicts between them, from both historical and contextual perspectives. I appreciate the author's diligence and the effort put into this work.

The author's meticulous approach is evident in the book, where he presents the views of various scholars on the historical differences between Judaism and Christianity regarding atonement and sacrifice, highlighting the diverse and conflicting interpretations of the event of the temple veil being torn. If we approach this from a purely historical-causal perspective, we may never reach a consensus. However, if we shift our focus to God's actions, we may see things differently, where individual lives can be transformed, and even the hatred between the two can be resolved.

Although humans are utterly tainted by sin, full of sinful nature and weaknesses, the unchanging God is determined to save sinners of the past, present, and future, for saving sinners is intrinsic to God's very nature. He does not wish for anyone to perish, but for all to repent. God's attributes are holiness, sanctity, glory (Kavod), and perfect love. He is a God who keeps His covenant and shows mercy, actively bringing His love to humanity, and dwelling with His people. His love descends like gravity to the sinners, accomplishing salvation. From the Old Testament to the New Testament, God's love is fulfilled through Jesus Christ. The New Testament does not replace the Old Testament but renews it. If we simply compare the two, we will only feel despair. But what God has done is to bring hope to His people. The New Testament and the Old Testament are like two brothers, testifying to God's salvation from Alpha to Omega. One must recognize God's absolute sovereignty and His attributes, otherwise, like the many theologians or historians mentioned in the book, one will engage in endless disputes over single events, cherry-picking or misinterpreting, only to prove one's own viewpoint. This not only creates hatred between Jews and Christians but may also lead to more divisions and fractures within the Christian church.

The book discusses the changes in sacrifices and the tearing of the temple veil. While the author mentions various opinions, I feel that the discussion lacks a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between God and His people, as represented by the temple. Moreover, the focus on "sacrifices bringing atonement for people" is something I cannot agree with. The subject of atonement, from Leviticus 16, is the Temple. We learn that on the Day of Atonement, the sacrifices were not

meant to atone for the people themselves but to cleanse the temple, where God dwells but had been defiled by the people's sins.

In the Old Testament era, the establishment of the temple manifested God's love, as He desired to dwell among sinful people. While God detailed the precise procedures for the Day of Atonement sacrifices, the forgiveness for the people did not come from the sacrifices themselves, but from the people's genuine repentance and humility before the Almighty God. Therefore, the discussion in Chapter 4 of the book on why the first Christians stopped making sacrifices is not the most important issue. We are all clear that the Roman authorities destroyed the temple, the subject of the Day of Atonement was removed, and the sacrifices were no longer physical, but as Paul said, a living sacrifice of one's life.

I agree with the author Jesper's point that the veil or the temple are not barriers between the relationship of man and God, but rather are the evidence of God's presence. However, the author did not supplement that the true thing that separates man from God is sin, and how God's love is manifested through the temple and the veil. The temple is God's dwelling place, and the veil represents the way to approach the presence of God.

And because God does not necessarily depend on the temple, but He counts on His own words. He sent His only begotten son Jesus Christ to His people, to become the ultimate and everlasting atonement for the people that He loves. Jesus is everything that atonement needs, He is the temple, He is the sacrifice, He is the Mercy Seat, He is the Scapegoat, who is blemish-free but bears the sins of all men, He is the high priest, He is the way, His body is the veil (Hebrews 10:20) and His blood cleanses all our sins, He is the Lamb that died for Heavenly Father's people.

If the tearing of the veil is interpreted as a sign of God's wrath, I would say the angry God would not have sent His Son to them, "But God demonstrates his own love for us in this: While we were still sinners, Christ died for us." (Romans 5:8) The death of Jesus Christ is to fulfill the forgiveness and salvation plan of God. And for Christians, we do not mock the root of the Cross but we celebrate the resurrection of Jesus Christ, that He is already the risen King, sitting at the right hand of God, interceding for His people.

Though the author Jesper takes into account the third interpretation that the tearing of the veil is an expression of Divine Sorrow, however, I do not quite agree with this. Taking this interpretation only from a human perspective, death is seen as sorrow. God is not the Father who tortures His only begotten Son, instead, we all know Jesus Christ conquered death. The victory of Jesus Christ is not presented in the human way that He came and claimed victory over the Roman Empire, He rather obeyed the Heavenly Father, descended from heaven, became the servant of all, and lived under the Law. The death of Jesus Christ is no longer a sorrow, and together with the resurrection of Christ has ultimately opened up the way to approach God's presence, allowing people to enter into God's presence (Hebrews 10:19-20) boldly.

As said, our God is an unchanging God who keeps His word. Regarding the author Jesper's intent to reconcile the misunderstanding between Jews and Christians, I would say the binding of Isaac (The Akedah) may serve a portion of the purpose. The Akedah is a significant moment in the religions of Judaism and Christianity, it exemplifies the willingness of the followers of God to listen to and obey His commands. The Jews today still have the Akedah printed on their prayer book, to remind themselves how God walked with their ancestor.

The Jews and the Christians believe in the same God who blesses His people, He sees our needs and provides. (Genesis 22:8) Both groups of people actually worship the same God every day through singing and praying. I don't agree that either group of people sublimated or substituted the sacrifice to be sanctified or forgiven, because the atonement has nothing to do with humans. Humans couldn't do anything to save themselves. It all relies on God's provision. God is the one who sublimated His covenant and substituted human sacrifice with the death and resurrection of His only begotten Son. God always takes action to save His people, what His people can do is to trust and believe.

Justification by faith (Romans 10:9-10) is the gift from the God who so loved His people. The Christians who have already taken this as the greatest present in life should have realized that the love of God is beyond what we could repay and that the Holy Spirit will lead us to live a life that glorifies our God, our Savior. We are no longer slaves of sin and the law because Jesus Christ already called an end to it, but

as we taste the love of God, we are willing to obey His commandments from the depths of our hearts. We repent every day, we grow and we learn to love the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac, and the God of Jacob with all our hearts, souls, minds, and strength (Deuteronomy 6:5 / Mark 12:30) and to love our neighbors as ourselves (Mark 12:31). It's not the mourning of death that leads us to love others, but the unconditional love of God moves us to draw closer to Him and live out the life purpose that serves the kingdom of God, that is to let others hear the "good news" that was brought to us by Jesus Christ.

God is the God who has everything, He doesn't need anything from us. Nonetheless, God created humans in the likeness of Himself, and to love our neighbors, who are in the image of God, is the best we can do to please our Lord. So to echo Jesper, Jews are created in the image of God, they are our neighbors whom God called us to love, instead of criticizing their wrongdoing or differences from Christians' belief, as we are all sinners God didn't grant us the right to judge and throw stones but only called us to love. The gravity of the love of God attracted us and saved us instead of His judgment by law. For me, I would say this is all Christian church members should remember and serve as our daily motto like the Jews printed the Akedah on their prayer book and read it daily.

As a Christian in Hong Kong, who witnessed all the conflicts and church schisms in recent years, seeing religious leaders twist the Bible to serve their political purposes, the course and these writings on reconciliation truly move me and remind me of the need to spread the gospel through love and live out the faith that God first loved us and granted us the grace of justification by faith.